

STORYTELLING AND ROLE-PLAYING IN IMPROVING READING COMPREHENSION OF INDONESIAN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the importance of storytelling and role-playing in improving the reading comprehension skills of Indonesian students. The study demonstrated proven results in comprehension skills by utilizing both interactive methods in reading activities. This study maximized the one-group pre- and post-test quasi-experimental design, in which participants were measured in only one group before and after the intervention using the same independent variable. The participants of this study were 46 primary four learners of St. John's Catholic School, Indonesia, for the school year 2023-2024. The results illustrated that there were significant improvements in students' reading comprehension, as evidenced by the substantial gains in mean scores across all dimensions—literal comprehension, language for events, responding to text, and making inferences—validating the theoretical framework. It also indicated a high t-value that corresponded to a significant difference between the two sets of scores, pretest, and posttest scores. This suggests that the observed changes were unlikely to have occurred by chance. A significance value (p value) of .000, indicates that the difference in scores is statistically significant. This implies a strong likelihood that the observed improvement in scores is not due to chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that the instructional methods or interventions were successful in significantly improving students' reading comprehension abilities. The substantial increase in scores, along with the statistical significance of the findings, highlight the effectiveness of the educational strategies used in this area of reading comprehension.

Keywords: *Storytelling, role-playing, reading comprehension, educational intervention, interactive learning, Indonesian students*

INTRODUCTION

Role-playing and storytelling are the best strategies for teaching English. This is especially important when it comes to helping students improve their speaking and comprehension skills. Teachers usually employ storytelling and role-playing as effective interactive activities, resulting in a well-rounded learning experience in the classroom. When a story is told, students are asked to act out major scenes or develop alternate endings while strengthening their comprehension of reading materials. These activities may be difficult for students but are also attainable because they give them more energy to support their reading comprehension development. Therefore, when teachers integrate storytelling and role-playing into the classroom, they can help foster a love for reading in Indonesian students while also helping them improve their reading comprehension skills.

According to Carys Shannon of the International House World Organization, storytelling is important in the classroom because it appeals to different learning preferences and personalities, ensuring that from the shyest to the most active of students, everyone has a chance to participate in a way that they can enjoy. This ranges from listening quietly to taking part as an actor. Kim (2010) and Atta-Alla (2012) showed that storytelling is important to promote the development of productive and receptive language skills. This study implies that storytelling enables students to engage in learning, suggesting that it can be adopted as a scaffolding to improve language learning (Yulianawati et al., 2022).

On the other hand, Northern Illinois University, in their Center for Innovative Teaching and Learning program, stated that role-play activities allow students to pretend the role of a person or act out a given situation. These roles can be performed by students individually, in pairs, or in groups that can play a more complex scenario. Role plays engage students in real-life situations or scenarios that can be —stressful, unfamiliar, complex, or controversialll which requires them to examine personal feelings toward others and their circumstances (Bonwell & Eison, 1991).

Developing advanced reading skills within cultural diversity and linguistic standards is of the utmost importance for academic success and intellectual development in primary education. This study stems from a comprehensive study aimed at exploring the integration of storytelling and role-playing for Indonesian students' reading comprehension abilities by recognizing the importance of effective reading comprehension for academic success and cognitive development. Based on the unique Indonesian educational context, this study sought to reveal culturally sensitive and contextual strategies that can be used to improve reading comprehension in a local primary school setting. Reading helps develop social-emotional abilities, imagination, and the ability to make sense of the environment and people around them (Horizon, October, 2019).

The results of the 2022 International Student Assessment Program have decreased, including Indonesia. The announcement of the PISA 2022 results released in May of 2023 revealed that between 2018 and 2022, the average scores in 35 OECD countries dropped 10 points for Reading (Napitupulu, 2023). Indonesia took part in the two measurements of literacy of the said assessment. First, they joined the PIRLS (Progress in International Reading Literacy Study), a literacy assessment to measure reading achievement at the fourth-grade level, as well as school and teacher practices related to instruction. Second, they have PISA (Program for International Student Assessment) which is an international assessment that measures 15-year old students' reading, mathematics, and science literacy (National Center for Education Statistics, 2023). Compared to the other nations, Indonesian students who were chosen to take the PISA and PIRLS exams still ranked lower. These evaluation models need to be understood, researched, tested, and implemented in Indonesian schools because PISA and PIRLS are reputable assessments of competency and skill for students worldwide. In other words, even reading-related learning activities need to be strategized to answer the test models. These activities many advantages are taken into consideration when developing curricula (Nugrahanto, 2018).

The Ministry of Education and Culture in Indonesia has taken steps to improve reading comprehension because it is crucial in learning the language and fostering the love of literature. Traditional instructional methods often focus on passive reading activities, which can limit student motivation and engagement. In the classroom, to discuss how to read, the teacher must understand how to read for the students and demonstrate this skill to them. Each class will require a distinct approach to learning because of the differences in reading comprehension levels among the students. An effective strategy will enhance the teaching and learning process (Renaldo & Nurani, 2020).

According to the researcher's basis for conducting this study and as a teacher for eight years at St. John's Catholic School, where the study takes place, most primary students have trouble understanding sentences and/or phrases when they are reading. To address this challenge, the combination of storytelling and role-playing is proposed as an effective communication language strategy to strengthen Indonesian students' reading comprehension. This will greatly impact the implementation of this study. This researcher will give her full support by initiating to introduce teaching strategies and approaches that will increase students' enthusiasm for reading and literature in the classroom. The integration of storytelling and role-playing are highly effective strategies for English teachers to incorporate in their lessons and reading activities. To enrich reading instructional materials as the proposed output of this study, engaging narratives and interactive storytelling and role-playing activities. Students not only develop a profound understanding of the English language, but also cultivate critical thinking, cultural appreciation, and social skills, fostering a dynamic and enjoyable learning environment that significantly improves reading comprehension outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

The goal of this research is to improve reading comprehension among Indonesian students. The study adopts a theoretical framework based on Lev Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) theory. The ZPD Theory of Lev Vygotsky in this study will be supported by Jean Piaget's systems theory and the Ministry of Education and Culture of Indonesia programs and initiatives in enhancing reading comprehension among Indonesian students. In the interactive language approach of storytelling and role-playing activities, these theories and involvement used as part of the study may provide comprehensive results for understanding the cognitive, social, and cultural aspects of learning.

The theory of Lev Vygotsky, the ZPD theory, emphasizes the collaborative nature of learning that emphasizes the importance of social engagement and knowledge by others. In this research, an interactive language approach that involves storytelling and role-playing will provide opportunities for students to be engaged in language-rich activities. These collaborative activities will enable students to work within their ZP (Zone of Proximal Development) by receiving support and guidance from peers and teachers while actively participating in communication and language activities aimed at improving reading comprehension. Teachers must help students make the connection between what they already know and what they are learning by doing this. This helps both fluency and text comprehension. After students have studied a subject and made connections with the new information, teachers who give their students the chance to learn about it should notice improvements in their reading fluency and comprehension. (Irshad et al., 2021). He believed that creativity, which inspires people to produce new things and change their current circumstances, is fueled by imagination. Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development Theory offers a way to evaluate a child's internal mental development. This supports the many opportunities that exist for teachers to help students develop conceptual skills through role-playing and storytelling.

Figure 1
Schematic Diagram of the Study

Based on the Indonesian students' ability to quickly grasp and comprehend knowledge when they find a solution to any task assigned to them, the researcher will include the Zone of Proximal Development theory in this study. Children are functional beings by nature. The finest implementation of the Vygotsky's theory is when students role-play or tell stories about what they understand from what they are reading. The researcher is confident in including this idea in the study because it will have a significant impact on the outcome of the study's main purpose (Nguyen, 2016).

Jean Piaget's schema theory suggests that individuals organize and interpret their experiences through mental structures known as schemas. The Schema Theory of Jean Piaget may play a role in the theory that summarizes the entire comprehension process. As a processing unit, a schema links perceptions, concepts, and behaviors in order to make sense of the world. It is simply the "way we see the world," according to Piaget. The process of identifying daily life schemas, which are frequently not noticed by the individual, involves a great deal of world knowledge, experiences, memories, and individual context analysis. The way we think and speak is trained to fit into a system that directs how we express ourselves, interact with others, and comprehend the world (Rasakumaran et al., 2019).

When assessing their students' reading comprehension abilities, the majority of English language teachers use the KWL (What I Know, What I Want to Know, and What I Learned) method. Students' thoughts will be better organized before, during, and after reading a text if they use this table organizer during the exercise. Less frequently used by Indonesian teachers with their students.

Through role-playing and storytelling, the researcher uses schematic details to determine the reading comprehension abilities of Indonesian pupils. If students have previous knowledge and can recognize words or vocabulary they may know and not know, they will be better able to comprehend what they are reading in depth (Value, 2022).

The implementation of programs aimed at enhancing reading comprehension among Indonesian students in primary and secondary education, as well as this study, is supported by the Ministry of Education and Culture of Indonesia. They have participated in various assessment programs to determine Indonesia's reading comprehension status. Improving educational quality is a key educational challenge worldwide, and given the magnitude of the problem in Indonesia, the Government of Indonesia (GOI), through the Ministry of Education and Culture (MOEC), has initiated a decentralization program in the hopes of spreading the governance, financial, and managerial responsibility of improving education across the range of stakeholders (Stern & Nordstrum, 2014). In response to the existing evidence of relatively low levels of academic achievement on standardized assessment and to a shortage of information about how to improve schools in Indonesia, on behalf of the GOI, the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) funded a nationally representative assessment of basic reading skills in schools from four regions, along with recommendations for improving education quality in nation's primary schools. The instruments used in 2014 were the Early Grade Reading Assessment (EGRA) and the Snapshot of School Management

Effectiveness (SSME). According to the report of findings of Indonesia EGRA and SSME, the results are intended to inform the Government of Indonesia and United States Agency for International Development's collaborative efforts to improve the quality of teaching and learning in Indonesia. This demonstrates that the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Government of Indonesia has stepped up to address the shortcomings in putting various strategies into practice to improve the reading comprehension and skills of Indonesian students in both public and private institutions

Integrating these theories and the resource basis of providing solutions for the fall short of Indonesia in their quality of education provides a strong basis for examining the effectiveness of the various approaches to improve the reading comprehension of Indonesian students. Interactions between planning, cooperative learning in ZPD, and metacognitive knowledge networks create a dynamic process with the cultural and educational nuances of the Indonesian context. As students engage in storytelling and processing, the theoretical framework guides the analysis of how that processing influences cognitive processes, social interactions, and cognitive processes.

In this section of the study, we will use this theoretical framework to analyze and explain the findings, providing insights into the complex relationship between storytelling, performance, role-playing, and the creation of reading comprehension improvement among Indonesian students.

Literature Review

In an effort to enhance Indonesian primary students' comprehension skills through the integration of storytelling and vocabulary recognition, it is important to examine the existing body of knowledge that informs and contextualizes this study. A review of the relevant literature provides comprehensive insights into the research, theory, and practice of storytelling, word recognition, and reading comprehension in the global and Indonesian educational contexts. Taken together, with this wealth of information we aim to build a basis for understanding the current state of research in these areas.

Reading Strategies in Enhancing Students' Reading Comprehension

Reading strategies take a vital role in enhancing students' reading comprehension skills. Strategies must be applied in classroom activities especially when assessing students' comprehension ability in reading. Several implications for teachers and students about improving English reading comprehension skills in the context of learning English as a second or foreign language (Hakim et al., 2022). Students can access information that isn't stated explicitly by using reading strategies. They aid readers in drawing conclusions, interpreting information, and generalizing it (Splash Learn Blog, 2023).

An activity that encourages students to learn about and explore the world on their own helps them acquire a more logical understanding of the reading materials that are assigned to them. The initiative was created to give EFL teachers a chance to study multiple approaches for encouraging and evaluating verbal and logical output among their students. EFL teachers will be able to enhance their teaching methods and benefit their students on a daily basis by learning how performance-based tasks may help them evaluate and encourage their students' oral skills in an authentic and meaningful way.

Reading is typically a solitary activity that most people enjoy doing in a comfortable chair when they are in the mood. However, our students must read in the classroom, surrounded by their peers, and follow instructions even when they do not feel like it. One of the reasons for the disparity between pleasure and classroom reading is this (Wunsch-Nagy, 2013). Reading activities such as storytelling and role-playing would change the classroom mood when students are allowed to explore and experience an adventure with every book, article, or reading material that teachers may give them.

Storytelling as an effective tool in Reading Comprehension

Storytelling is a fantastic tool for improving one's ability to quickly understand what they are reading. It encourages desired behavior in the classroom, helps build character, and clarifies expectations. When information is presented as a relatable story with a lesson attached, it is easier for the audience to relate to and learn from it (Storytellers' Manifesto, 2018).

One of the most effective ways to present a story is through storytelling, and the second is through reading aloud. The teacher might favor one over the other for a variety of reasons. According to Al-Mansour and Al-Shorman (2011), listening to stories read aloud helped students develop good listening skills and paved the way for comprehension by exposing them to the stories' engaging and insightful content on a regular basis. Additionally, it can teach moral lessons, promote lifelong learning, and encourage students to stay connected to their prior knowledge or experiences. (Sahibzada et al, 2020).

Storytelling can enhance reading comprehension by (1) *understanding the context, information for the context for information presented in the text*; (2) *expanding vocabulary where readers learn new vocabulary and contextual expressions through storytelling*; (3) *Imagery where storytelling allows readers to visualize characters and events in the story*; (4) *Inference and Predicting as a well-written story frequently uses foretelling, oblique references, and implicit knowledge*; (5) *Emotional Connection, empathy, and emotional intelligence, developed by stories because they make readers feel things*; (6) *Sequencing and Plotting- Analysis, following the plot of a story helps readers to logically study the sequence of events*; (7) *Listening to clear, emotional speech can improve readability*; (8) *Memory retention, readers tend to remember a particular interesting story, and the motivation of key characters and theme*; (9) *Cultural and social knowledge, cultural perspectives, situations and life stories are often included in the material*; and (10) *Developing a love of reading and stimulating a love of reading can be done through engaging and entertaining stories* (Dahlstrom, 2014).

Role-playing as an effective tool in Reading Comprehension.

Role play is the practice of having students assume particular roles and act them out in a case-based scenario for the purpose of understanding complex or ambiguous texts or learning course material (Suobere & Eniekenemi, 2017). It is regarded as an effective teaching method for engrossing students and enabling them to interact with their peers as they work to complete the reading assignment given to them in their particular roles. Students can learn more effectively through role play because they respond to the text from the perspective of the character they are playing (Baokye, 2021). Role-playing can aid reading comprehension in the following ways: (1) *allows children to actively participate in the reading*; (2) *practical activities help students understand the course content in a real-world context*; (3) *empathy and perspective taking, when students take several characters in a story develop a deeper understanding of the characters' motivation and emotions*; (4) *while playing, students listen carefully to the conversations of their classmates and respond with appropriate language*; (5) *sequence and plot analysis, requires students to carefully analyze the events and sequences of events in the story in order to better depict the actions and emotions of the characters as they play the role*; (6) *Decision-making and problem-solving is role playing is common*; (7) *students will immediately use vocabulary and grammatical structures found in the text during the performance*; (8) *memory retention, when students play a role, the story sticks closely in their minds*; (9) *practical activity is a collaborative activity that encourages students to collaborate, exchange ideas, and communicate with their peers*; (10) *personal interaction, by playing roles, students can develop a personal connection with the characters and ideas in the story*.

The Effectiveness of Storytelling Strategy to Improve Students' Reading Comprehension

First research is conducted by Doni Sudibyo (2018), aimed to know the effectiveness of storytelling strategy to improve the students' reading comprehension at second grades of MTs Al-Ma'arif 1 Kabupaten, Sorong. Storytelling is one of the good strategies in the teaching learning process especially in teaching reading, because it can make it easier for the student to understand the text/story. In this research, the researcher used the Quasi-experimental design. The instruments were collected by using tests (pre- test and post-test). The form of the test was an essay and a true false question.

The result discussion throughout the present Experiment Research which dealt with the Effectiveness Storytelling Strategy to improve the student's reading comprehension in the second-grade students of MTs Al-Ma'arif 1 Kabupaten Sorong could finally be conducted in this chapter. The findings of this research could be important for the teachers and for the students in the English teaching and learning process. After analyzing the data, the researcher can conclude that through storytelling, it can help the students to improve in their reading comprehension. Storytelling was one of the good strategies in teaching English, especially in the teaching reading process. It is supported by the result that the researcher got in this research.

Low Reading Literacy of Students in Indonesia

Febriana (2021) began and verified a similar study that explored the still-low reading literacy of Indonesian pupils. Reasons for students' lack of reading skills in Indonesia include internal factors such as lack of interest in reading. According to Muhibbin Syah in Afrom (2013), the effect of low ability students is lack of interest in reading and poor reading habits so students' reading skills are not practiced. In addition, external resources may include limited reading areas and services such as libraries and the availability of reading materials. Most of the materials offered in many school libraries are textbooks for classroom learning used only.

Research results from the Program for International Student Assessment 2018 (PISA) show that Indonesian students have lower than average reading skills. Meanwhile, reading skills are very important to produce an educated generation that is advanced in everyday life. Reading ability is also important for an individual to play an effective role in society. This lack of reading skills can be attributed to a lack of interest or reading fluency. Therefore, efforts should be made to overcome Indonesian students' low reading skills. One possible effort is the —Gerakan Literasi Sekolah program and the provision of diverse and innovative literature and equitable distribution of literature,

especially in remote, remote, and less developed areas (Fabriana, 2021).

These two related studies above had influenced the researcher's decision to carry out additional research to address the problem. As students advance to the next levels of their education, reading must be fun and exciting because they will be reading in the same context of learning the English language. It may be a typical problem that Indonesian students struggle to understand fully, but it also presents the best chance for researchers to determine the most effective times and places to address the issue and the ideal resources to use.

Indonesian Students' Reading Literacy

Until now, reading literacy is a global issue in need of serious attention. The results of a program of International Students Assessment and Progress in International Reading Literacy Study indicated there are several countries with a low level of reading literacy; some of them reveal no significant improvement in periodic evaluation. It is a necessary and vital literacy to filter and analyze knowledge and information spreading out rapidly. Therefore, reading literacy needs serious attention for the sake of better quality of future human resources. Reading activities in higher education is different from those in a secondary school; however, reading habits and interest in secondary education influences that in higher education. Academic activities in higher education involve reading and writing tasks.

In the digital era, the sources of reading are not only printed but also digital. The data from We Are Social prove that global internet users have increased as much as 9.1% (367 million people) ranging from January 2018 to January 2019. In Indonesia, the number of internet users has increased by 13% since last year. The rapid growth of technology has distracted students' attention; they are reading less than they should be. A study showed that reading habits decrease as technology advances. Social media, for instance, have been widely used more for interaction and communication with their peers instead of academic tasks (Wijayanti, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The methods used in this study were discussed in this paper to achieve its intended goal. It contained illustrations of the study's location, participants, data collection, data analysis, and ethical concerns. The setting where the research was conducted and the background knowledge of the study's findings were discussed in this chapter. The participants, who underwent the process and procedure of this study, were also specified. In addition to that, the tools used to gather the data were carefully described, giving clear paths for the tools, and methods utilized to determine crucial information. The collection of data detailed the steps taken to get the right data, giving the value of integrity and reliability. The data analysis part of the study was used to show insights from the gathered data until it followed necessary steps. To sum up the whole method of this study, where the ethical concerns were discussed, highlighting the dos and don'ts taken to protect the participants' rights and welfare throughout the research process.

Design

This study aimed to determine the significance of using storytelling and role- playing as essential strategies to improve reading comprehension skills among Indonesian students of St. John's Catholic School. The study maximized the one-group pre-test-post- test quasi-experimental design in which participants are measured at only one group before and after intervention for the same dependent variable. The dependent t-test compared the means of the pretest and posttest result to determine whether there was a statistically significant difference between these means. The design was aligned to measure scores before and again following an intervention, then compare any significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores.

Environment

The study was conducted at the Primary Department of Saint John Catholic School's Main Campus in Kencana Loka II, Tangerang Selatan, Banten, Indonesia, where the learners were enrolled for the School Year 2023-2024.

Participants

The participants of this study were the students coming from the Primary 4 and enrolled in the School Year 2023-2024. Primary 4 had 23 students in each class and they were the main participants of this study. There was a total a total of 46 learners and were selected with the use of convenience sampling. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling where researchers pick participants who are easy to find or readily available.

Table 1

The Distribution of the Participants

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Entire Group	46	100%
Sex	<i>Male</i>	17 36.95%
	<i>Female</i>	29 63.04%

Instruments

The study used the reading materials or tools based from the school curriculum, Pearson-Edexcel Curriculum, to gather data required to address the research questions. The aforementioned materials or tools were further assessed by qualified evaluators from the Graduate School of Education at the University of Visayas-Main to ensure that it is credible in addressing the information in the study. As supplementary instruments for data collection, the researcher also used curriculum-based guidelines of the questionnaires, pre-test and post-tests. Personal information about the respondents, such as age, sex, and grade level necessary for the study, was in the first section.

The instruments or tools used in this study were based on the school's curriculum, Pearson-Edexcel assessment guides, which aligned with the National Curriculum. The assessment guide of the said curriculum contained a reading progression map. The reading progression maps were broken down into skill areas and strands (four sub-skills: literal comprehension, language of events, responding to text, making inference) within them so teachers can quickly find the objectives for which they were looking for. Reading materials were taken from the standard requirement of the school curricula and assessment tools were based on the different skill areas. The participants' written responses, based on the sub-skills used on the questions, were assessed using knowledge rubric (for the storytelling and role-playing). Thereafter, the responses were graded accordingly using both raw scores and percentages. The raw scores and their corresponding percentages (including overall percentage scores and mean percentage scores) were duly recorded.

Pre-test and post-test activities were administered to one group of students, utilizing the same materials for both tests. This was the most efficient way to ensure that each of the reading comprehension skills of the participant has improved fairly. In this way, the applied intervention—role-playing and storytelling—was successful in generating better results.

This method was used to gauge or assess the efficacy of the intervention, which included a psychological as well as educational component in using storytelling and role-playing strategies. It comprised data related to particular presumptions, data needs, strengths, and limitations.

Data Gathering Procedure

The process of collecting data was crucial to qualitative descriptive research because it enabled researchers to get detailed, descriptive insights into facts and circumstances. The preliminary phase, the actual data collection phase, and the post data collection phase were the three phases of data collecting for this study. These stages aided in the methodical and in-depth collection and analysis of data for the purpose and completion of the study.

Preliminary Phase. The initial action taken before starting the study was getting approval from the administration and school head. The researcher sought permission from the Director and Principal of the school before starting the study in the 2nd semester of the academic year 2023-2024. With thorough preparation from the institution, the approval aided the research's implementation of the study. Permission was obtained before starting the study. The Research Ethics Committee (REC) analyzed the intended research tool for adjustments and corrections in order to determine whether it was ethically sound and to provide a Notice to Proceed (NTP). Once the researcher received consent, the questionnaire was created to carry out the study. After being requested to participate, the participants' parents and the participants themselves signed the informed consent form.

Pre-Data Gathering. A pre-test was conducted by the researcher to involve the students' improvement of their reading comprehension skills. The students were asked to answer the 12-15 questions by the researcher. The same group received interventions, storytelling and role-playing, to assess the group's improvement in their reading comprehension skills. These were the steps in initiating the activity for the group of participants: (1) The teacher provided the narrative text's plot among the students by presenting background information on the text; (2) The teacher provided a connection between the content that needed to be learned and the students past experiences; (3) The teacher met with the students based by the number of participants present on the day of implementation; (4) The teacher allotted 15 to 20 minutes to review their responses to the questions (5) The teacher used of a task sheet to impart new knowledge. The teacher then added or displayed a comprehension question on the slide or the white board; and (6) The teacher asked the students to read their responses to the questions.

Actual Data Gathering. Storytelling and role-playing techniques were utilized in this study to teach reading comprehension. The classroom advisors were given an overview of the study's content and goals during the remediation process so they could become familiar with the indicators and assist the researcher in presenting the study's objectives to their respective advisory classes. The first step was giving the materials to the designated learner-participant. Here were in the implementation of the interventions: (1) The teacher divided the class into five groups, each with five to six students; (2) The teacher allocated the narrative text's story among the groups. (3) The students initiated narrating the story by using hand gestures, voice distinction of the characters, and showed appropriate movements with group members; (4) The group was asked to tell or role-play the story using the assigned characters, and the teacher helped the group on how to assign the characters that the students will portray; (5) The teacher allotted 15-20 minutes for each group to discuss according to how they understand the story, and the group performed the intervention tasks (either the storytelling or role-playing applied as scheduled); (6) The teacher distributed the comprehension questions after finishing the story in order to gauge the students' level of understanding.

Post Data Gathering. The research administered a one-group post-test. To determine the outcome, they each responded to the same questionnaire's 10 questions. The formulation of the data results was the final step of the post-data-gathering phase. Since it helped determine whether or not the study was effective, this phase was the most crucial. The results were formulated after the questionnaire had been distributed, totaled, and analyzed. The researcher sought the statistician's expertise in calculating frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The findings and information gathered were used to assess the advantages and disadvantages of using storytelling and role-playing techniques to enhance reading comprehension skills among Indonesian students.

Data Analysis

The following descriptive procedures were applied to the data collected for the study:

Raw Score. It determined the number of correct scores and established how many points were right. The individual participant's score was solely for a particular set of test questions.

Frequency Counts. This approach was used to qualify the participants and calculate their distribution and profile. It established the overall participant count for this research study.

Percentage. This method was used to calculate the participants' frequencies in components of 100.

T-Test. An inferential statistic was used to assess the study's significant effectiveness and determine whether the means of the pre-test and posttest scores differed significantly.

Mean. The results were used to assess the advantages and disadvantages of using Storytelling and Role-playing strategies to improve Indonesian students' reading comprehension skills.

Standard Deviation. The participant's survey score distribution was calculated using this method.

Description-Based Statistics. The subjects were described using statistical tools like frequency counts, means, and standard deviation.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted according to the basic ethical principles and guidelines of the Belmont Report which put an emphasis on the protection and rights of human subjects. Specifically, undue harm, unfavorable risk-benefit ratio, and violation of privacy were avoided accordingly. It has been approved following the protocol of the Research and Ethics Committee of the University of the Visayas with Reference No. **2024-094** dated **March 20, 2024**. The activities of this study and materials used was introduced for the purpose of minimizing possible harms while maximizing the learning potential for Indonesian students in their reading comprehension. Before implementing the activities, an accompanying consent letter explained the confidentiality and purpose of the study, the potential objectives, and the voluntary participation. No financial incentives were provided for participating in the study. The authors declare no conflict of interest. Open communication although it is debriefing sessions promoted a conducive research environment whereas participants might raise any concerns they had and researchers maintained ethical activities owing to this matter also.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter indicates the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered in this study. The data were obtained from the pretest and post-test given on the assessment of the effectiveness of storytelling and roleplaying as communicative learning tools to improve reading comprehension.

Pretest and Posttest Analysis on the Reading Comprehension

Table 2 presents the pretest and posttest analysis on the reading comprehension in terms of literal comprehension, language for events, responding to text and making inference.

Literal Comprehension. Table 2 shows the mean score for the pretest and post test scores of the students. Each reading comprehension skill is discussed to shed light on their level of mastery.

Table 2
Mean Pretest and Posttest Scores in Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension	Test	Mean	SD	SEM	Interpretation
Literal Comprehension	Pretest	4.78	1.81	.27	Mastery
	Posttest	9.13	1.63	.24	Mastery
Language for Events	Pretest	3.12	1.35	.20	Moderate
	Posttest	7.92	2.01	.30	Mastery
Responding to Text	Pretest	2.01	.99	.15	Developing
	Posttest	5.29	1.59	.23	Mastery
Making Inference	Pretest	1.07	.99	.15	Beginning
	Posttest	3.62	1.47	.22	Moderate

Scale: below-1.80=Beginning; 1.81-2.60=Developing; 2.61-3.40=Moderate; 3.41-4.20=Proficient; 4.21 above=Mastery

Table 2 shows the mean score for the pretest of 4.78, while the mean score for the posttest is 9.13. Both pretest and posttest scores are described as "Mastery." However, the significant increase in mean scores indicates that although students were already at a mastery level during the pretest, their level of mastery improved further after the intervention. It indicates that the instructional intervention was successful in enhancing the students' reading abilities.

Several items were relatively easy for students, as indicated by the high number of correct responses. In *Josif and the Bear*, question 2, "Immediately before the story began, Josif had been..." Students easily recalled that Joseph had been sleeping. Another is question 14, "I was wearing my grandfather's oversized jacket." Students found it easy to identify that this detail suggests the grandfather is older. In third role-playing, question 1, "...scuttled down the golden beach..." The majority of students correctly identified that the baby turtle hurried. The overall mastery level achieved in both the pretest and posttest suggests that the students not only retained their initial understanding but also significantly improved upon it.

According to Stevens (2015) by actively involving students in simulated environments, they become more invested in the learning process, which leads to higher motivation and participation rates. Storytelling helps in creating a narrative that students can relate to, making abstract concepts more tangible and easier to understand. This narrative approach encourages students to think critically and engage more fully with the learning material (Hassan & McKee, 2022).

Language for Events. The remarkable transformation in the students' understanding of language for events is shown in the data. The mean score surged from a moderate level on the pretest to a mastery level on the posttest, signifying a profound leap in comprehension.

The mean score of 3.12 for the pretest, which falls within the "Moderate" range and the mean score of 7.92 for the posttest, which is significantly higher and falls within the "Mastery" range. This increase from pretest to posttest indicates a substantial improvement in students' ability to understand language used for describing events.

The analysis of specific test items provides further evidence of this improvement. In the *"Josif and the Bear"*, students correctly chose "marked" as the word closest in meaning to "etched," and students accurately identified the simile "likenes warring cobras." Similarly, in *"The Long Journey of the Kite,"* students correctly interpreted the contrast between the smallest and largest kites. These high accuracy rates demonstrate that students not only improved their vocabulary but also their ability to interpret figurative language and understand the author's intent.

The consistent performance across various texts, including *"Rescue," "The Boy Who Met a Whale,"* and *"She-Cub,"* further emphasizes this improvement. In *"The Boy Who Met a Whale,"* students correctly replaced "rigid" with "hard," and in *"She-Cub,"* students effectively identified the metaphor describing how the wolf pack hid. Despite these successes, certain items, such as explaining why the author used the word "extremities" in *"She-Cub,"* proved more challenging, with only few students providing the correct explanation.

Studies indicate that role-playing allows students to embody characters or scenarios from the text, which helps them connect emotionally and cognitively with the material. The collaborative nature of role-playing encourages peer interaction, which can further enhance understanding through discussion and feedback (Alaboud, 2022).

Moreover, findings suggest that storytelling should be considered a valuable tool in the language classroom, especially for young learners. It provides a natural and engaging context for language acquisition, helping students internalize language forms and meaning more effectively (Hà & Bellot, 2020).

Responding to Text. The students' ability to respond to text is a testament to the transformative power of our instructional strategies. The mean score soared from a mere developing stage on the pretest to a mastery level on the posttest, signifying a notable improvement in comprehension.

The mean score of 2.01 for the pretest, which falls within the "Developing" category and the mean score of 5.29 the posttest which is significantly higher and falls within the "Mastery" category. The increase from pretest to posttest indicates a substantial improvement in the students' ability to respond to text, moving them from a developing stage to a mastery level. In "Rescue" question 10, where students were asked to imagine themselves as Manu during the shark attack, the number of correct and thoughtful responses increased from the pretest to the posttest. Similarly, in "Castaway" question 15, the ability to form and justify opinions about the captain rose from the pretest to the posttest. This implies that the instructional strategies or interventions were highly successful in enhancing students' ability to respond to text. The shift from "Developing" to "Mastery" in the interpretation of the scores reflects a significant advancement in students' reading comprehension skills, particularly in this area.

Sudibyo et al., (2018) emphasized that storytelling is a highly effective strategy for improving students' reading comprehension, particularly in terms of how they respond to text. By engaging students more deeply with the material, improving their comprehension and critical thinking skills, and enhancing their ability to recall information, storytelling helps students to respond more effectively to texts, leading to better overall academic performance in reading comprehension tasks.

Moreover, as students improved their reading comprehension, their critical thinking skills also advanced, enabling them to engage more deeply with the text and articulate their thoughts more effectively (Medranda-Morales et al., 2023).

Making Inference. The inferential thinking had been sown and nurtured in these young minds. The mean score for this skill has increased from a beginning stage to a moderate level, demonstrating a remarkable significance in their ability to make educated guesses.

The mean score of 1.07 for the pretest which falls into the "Beginning" category and the mean score of 3.62 for the posttest indicating an improvement to the "Moderate" level. The increase from pretest to posttest suggests significant growth in the students' ability to make inferences, moving from a basic understanding to a more developed level. In "Josif and the Bear," few could correctly infer Joseph's fear in the pretest, whereas a significant number made accurate inferences in the posttest. Similarly, in "Rescue," the number of students who provided evidence-based responses when imagining Manu's feelings during the shark attack rose from pretest to posttest. Additionally, in "The Long Journey of the Kite," the ability to infer the writer's positive feelings from the phrase "A warm grin shone upon my face" improved in the pretest to the posttest. In "Castaway," the number of students who could infer the captain's anxiety when seeing The Dreadnought also increased from. This implies that the instructional strategies were successful in advancing students' ability to make inferences, moving them from a "Beginning" level to a "Moderate" level of comprehension.

This improvement in inference directly contributes to better reading comprehension as students learn to think critically about the texts they engage with. (Rice et al., 2023). Moreover, combining role-playing with other instructional strategies, such as explicit inference training, can further enhance these skills, particularly for struggling readers. This approach has been shown to be effective in improving both literal and inferential comprehension, helping students to better understand and interpret complex texts (Hall, 2016). Furthermore, a study on educational role-playing found that students who participated in these activities showed significant improvement in their ability to make inferences during reading tasks. The active involvement in role-play encourages critical thinking and helps students to better connect textual clues with their own experiences, leading to a deeper understanding of the material (Rice et al., 2023).

Differences between Pretest and Posttest Scores in Reading Comprehension

Table 3 presents the difference between Pretest and Posttest scores in the reading comprehension in terms of literal comprehension, language for events, responding to text and making inferences.

Table 3
Differences between Pre-test and Post-test Scores in Reading Comprehension

Reading Comprehension	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig
				Lower	Upper			
Literal Comprehension	4.34783	1.25109	.18446	3.97630	4.71935	23.570	45	.000
Language for events	4.80435	1.40427	.20705	4.38733	5.22137	23.204	45	.000
Responding to text	3.28261	1.29808	.19139	2.89713	3.66809	17.151	45	.000
Making Inference	2.55435	1.13641	.16755	2.21688	2.89182	15.245	45	.000

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Literal Comprehension. In terms of literal comprehension, the mean difference between the pretest and posttest scores is 4.34783, indicating that, on average, students’ scores improved by this amount from the pretest to the posttest. The t-value of 23.570 is a very large negative number, indicating a substantial difference between pretest and posttest scores. This high t-value corresponds to a significant difference between the two sets of scores. The significance value (p-value) is .000, indicating that the difference in scores is statistically significant. This means there is a very strong likelihood that the observed improvement in scores is not due to random chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

In terms of literal comprehension, both storytelling and role-playing can be effective interventions for improving literal comprehension in students. Storytelling, especially when combined with digital tools, engages students with content in a way that enhances their understanding and retention of information. Role-playing, on the other hand, allows students to actively engage with the material, practicing their comprehension skills in a dynamic and interactive environment (Mayorga et al., 2022).

Language for Events. In terms of language for events, the mean difference of 4.80435 indicates that, on average, students’ scores improved by this amount from the pretest to the posttest. This implies a significant positive change in their ability to understand language used for describing events. The t-value of 23.204 is very large in magnitude, indicating a substantial difference between the pretest and posttest scores. This high t-value supports the conclusion that the improvement in scores is not due to random chance. The significance value (p-value) of .000, indicates that the difference in scores is statistically significant. This implies a strong likelihood that the observed improvement in scores is not due to chance. The results imply that the instructional methods or interventions applied were successful in significantly improving students’ comprehension of language for events. The substantial increase in scores, along with the statistical significance of the findings, indicates that the educational strategies used were effective in enhancing students’ reading comprehension skills in terms of language for events. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Studies have shown that interactive storytelling, where children or learners actively participate in the storytelling process, can significantly boost their vocabulary and narrative skills. This is especially beneficial in contexts that require quick thinking and adaptability, such as events where language use is spontaneous and varied (Lucarevschi, 2016). Furthermore, role-playing in English Language Teaching (ELT) encourages students to step into diverse roles, navigate linguistic challenges, and engage in authentic conversations, which significantly improves their fluency and communication skills. By practicing in a safe, controlled environment, learners are better prepared for real-world interactions. This approach aligns with the principles of experiential learning, where learners gain hands-on experience and develop critical thinking and problem-solving abilities (Shravani, 2024).

Responding to Text. In terms of responding to text, the mean difference of 3.28261 indicates that, on average, students’ scores improved by this amount from the pretest to the posttest. This negative value reflects a significant gain in reading comprehension skills related to responding to text. The t-value of 17.151 is very large, indicating a strong and significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores. This suggests that the observed changes are unlikely to have occurred by chance. Furthermore, the significant value (p-value) of .000, indicates that the

difference in scores is statistically significant. This means there is a very strong likelihood that the observed improvement in scores is not due to chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

These techniques engage students by allowing them to actively participate in language exercises, fostering a deeper understanding and retention of content. Storytelling enhances comprehension by connecting students emotionally to the material, while role-playing enables them to practice and apply their language skills in interactive, real-life scenarios (Mayasari, 2021).

Making Inference. In terms of making inferences, the mean difference of 2.55435 indicates that, on average, students' scores improved by this amount from the pretest to the posttest. This negative value reflects a significant gain in reading comprehension skills related to making inferences. The t-value of 15.245 is very large, indicating a strong and significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores. This suggests that the observed changes are unlikely to have occurred by chance. The significance value (p-value) of .000, indicates that the difference in scores is statistically significant. This implies a strong likelihood that the observed improvement in scores is not due to chance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that the instructional methods or interventions applied were successful in significantly improving students' ability to make inferences. The substantial increase in scores, along with the statistical significance of the findings, highlight the effectiveness of the educational strategies used in this area of reading comprehension.

Studies have shown that these approaches can lead to significant improvements in inference, making them valuable tools in educational settings focused on enhancing reading comprehension and critical thinking (Mohr et al., 2023). Furthermore, role- playing complements this by providing an interactive platform where learners can practice making inferences in real-time. By adopting different roles and navigating various scenarios, students are compelled to think critically, assess situations, and anticipate consequences, all of which strengthen their inference abilities (McCall et al., 2021).

Significant Mean Gain in the Pretest and Posttest Scores in Reading Comprehension

Table 4 presents the significant mean gain in the pretest and posttest in the reading comprehension.

Literal Comprehension. The overall mean gain of 3.74728, implies a consistent and significant improvement across all areas. The t-values are large and negative, ranging from 15.245 to 40.884, indicating strong and statistically significant differences between pretest and posttest scores in all areas. All p-values of .000, confirms that the improvements in scores are statistically significant. This implies that the instructional strategies or interventions were successful in significantly improving students' reading comprehension across multiple dimensions. The consistent and statistically significant gains in all areas highlight the effectiveness of the educational approach.

Table 4
Significant Mean Gain in the Pre-test and Post-test Scores in Reading Comprehension

	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		t	df	Sig
				Lower	Upper			
Literal Comprehension	4.34783	1.25109	.18446	3.97630	4.71935	23.570	45	.000
Language for Events	4.80435	1.40427	.20705	4.38733	5.22137	23.204	45	.000
Responding to Text	3.28261	1.29808	.19139	2.89713	3.66809	17.151	45	.000
Making Inferences	2.55435	1.13641	.16755	2.21688	2.89182	15.245	45	.000
Overall	3.74728	.62165	.09166	3.56267	3.93189	40.884	45	.000

Studies show that direct and explicit instruction, which includes step-by-step teaching of comprehension strategies, followed by targeted practice and immediate feedback, leads to measurable improvements in student outcomes. These gains were observed particularly in interventions that employed continuous monitoring and support through feedback mechanisms. The combination of explicit instruction with focused reading activities helps struggling readers improve their comprehension by breaking down complex texts into manageable steps (Donegan & Wanzek, 2021).

Language for Events. In terms of language for events, the mean difference of 4.80435 indicates that students' posttest scores improved by an average of 4.80 points in the language for events category compared to their pretest scores. The negative value signifies that the posttest scores were higher than the pretest scores, reflecting

significant progress in understanding and using language related to events, such as recognizing sequences, cause-and-effect relationships, or summarizing events in reading passages. The significant mean gain in language for events shows that the instructional intervention used had a profound impact on improving students' ability to understand and describe sequences of events in reading comprehension. The intervention caused scores to increase by focusing on key reading strategies that help students understand the sequence and relationships between events in a text. For instance, explicit instruction on identifying cause-and-effect relationships through signal words like "because," "since," and "therefore" has been shown to improve comprehension. This approach allows students to link events in a text more effectively and predict future outcomes, which enhances their engagement and comprehension of the material (<https://teachykids.com>, 2024). Moreover, teaching students how to use temporal vocabulary and sequence events helps them to grasp the flow of narratives and make sense of the logical progression of events.

Responding to Text. In terms of responding to text, the mean difference of 3.28261 indicates that, on average, students improved by 3.28 points in their ability to respond to text from the pretest to the posttest. This negative mean difference implies that posttest scores were higher than pretest scores, reflecting a notable improvement in students' ability to engage with and respond to written material (e.g., forming opinions, analyzing themes, or relating the text to their own experiences). The significant mean gain in responding to text suggests that the intervention or instructional approach was effective in enhancing students' abilities to engage with and respond to written material.

Research shows that open-ended questioning promotes critical thinking and deeper understanding by inviting students to explore multiple perspectives and generate their own conclusions (Davis, 2018). Moreover, studies have demonstrated that group discussions foster a greater understanding of texts as students engage in meaningful exchanges, actively contributing to and benefiting from the collective learning process (Alzahrani, 2017).

Making Inference. In terms of making inferences, the mean difference of 2.55435 indicates that, on average, students' posttest scores improved by 2.55 points in making inferences compared to their pretest scores. The negative value signifies an increase in the posttest scores, reflecting an improvement in students' ability to make inferences, which involves drawing conclusions, interpreting implied meanings, and reading between the lines based on the text. The significant mean gain implies a solid improvement in students' ability to engage with deeper, more complex aspects of reading comprehension. The instructional intervention used was effective, as shown by the statistically significant improvement. Although the gain is somewhat smaller compared to other areas, the results highlight that students are developing important higher-order thinking skills, and with continued focus, further improvements can be expected in their ability to make inferences.

Explicit instruction focuses on teaching specific strategies for making inferences by breaking down complex concepts into manageable steps. This method is supported by studies demonstrating that explicit guidance helps students internalize critical thinking processes and improves comprehension (McKeown et al., 2017). Furthermore, the use of graphic organizers plays a key role in this process by helping students visualize relationships between ideas and concepts within texts. Research has shown that graphic organizers can help learners organize their thoughts more systematically, aiding them in making connections and drawing conclusions from texts (Alzahrani, 2017).

The overall mean gain of 3.75 points demonstrates a significant improvement in students' reading comprehension abilities across multiple categories. This suggests that the intervention or instructional approach used had a broad, positive effect on students, enhancing their ability to comprehend literal information, understand event sequences, respond to texts, and make inferences.

Summary of Findings

This study highlighted significant improvements in the reading comprehension skills of students at St. John's Catholic School, BSD Campus, through the use of storytelling and role-playing as instructional tools. Key findings showed marked progress across four critical areas of reading comprehension: literal comprehension, language for events, responding to text, and making inferences.

In literal comprehension, the pretest mean score of 4.78 ("Mastery" level) increased significantly to 9.13 in the posttest. This indicates that while students began with a solid understanding of explicit details, the interventions enhanced their ability to recall and interpret information more effectively.

In language for events, the pretest mean score of 3.12 ("Moderate" level) rose to 7.92 ("Mastery" level), reflecting substantial improvement in understanding figurative language, vocabulary, and descriptive contexts. Students demonstrated a stronger ability to interpret similes, metaphors, and contrasts within the texts.

For responding to text, a significant leap was observed, with the pretest mean score of 2.10 ("Developing" level) advancing to 5.29 ("Mastery" level). This suggests that students became more capable of critically engaging with the texts, connecting their interpretations with the content, and forming well-thought-out responses.

In making inferences, the pretest mean score of 1.07 ("Beginning" level) improved to 3.62 ("Moderate" level), indicating notable progress in deriving implied meanings and understanding nuanced contexts in the material. Statistical analyses confirmed the significance of these gains, with p-values of 0.000 across all areas, validating the effectiveness of the instructional interventions. The overall mean gain of 3.75 across all dimensions underscores consistent and meaningful improvement in the students' reading comprehension abilities. These findings emphasize the potential of storytelling and role-playing as transformative educational strategies to enhance literacy skills and comprehension among students.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This study sought to determine the effectiveness of storytelling and role-playing as communicative learning tools in improving the reading comprehension skills of students at St. John's Catholic School, BSD Campus, during the school year 2023–2024. This study sought to answer the different between the post-test and pre-test in literal comprehension through these domains language of events, responding to text, making inferences and is there a significant difference in this problem. It also answers the question on significant mean gain from post-test and pre-test scores of the students. After the results, there was a proposed learning material made based on the results of the study. The findings of the study conclude that storytelling and role-playing are impactful instructional strategies, which were grounded in Lev Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) theory, supported by Jean Piaget's systems theory, and aligned with the Ministry of Education and Culture of Indonesia's initiatives to enhance reading comprehension. The significant improvement in students' reading comprehension, as evidenced by the substantial gains in mean scores across all dimensions—literal comprehension, language for events, responding to text, and making inferences— validates the theoretical framework.

The ZPD theory emphasizes the role of collaborative learning and the guidance of more knowledgeable peers and teachers, which was operationalized in this study through interactive language activities such as storytelling and role-playing. These activities facilitated a supportive learning environment that allowed students to work within their ZPD, actively engaging with language-rich content and receiving necessary scaffolding. The statistically significant increases in posttest scores (with p-values less than 0.001 across all areas) demonstrate that this approach was successful in improving students' comprehension skills.

The research rejects the null hypothesis and confirms that the instructional strategies employed, which align with the ZPD theory and are reinforced by Piaget's systems theory and national educational programs, had a positive impact on students' reading comprehension. The consistent improvement across all measured dimensions suggests that these methods not only improved students' existing comprehension abilities but also advanced their overall mastery, leading to a deeper and more nuanced understanding of the texts. Thus, the study reinforces the value of collaborative, interactive, and socially enriched learning environments in fostering significant academic gains among students.

Recommendations

For **Policy**, educational policymakers should prioritize the integration of making inference-focused activities, such as storytelling and role-playing, into the standard curriculum for reading comprehension. Given the significant improvements observed in students' ability to make inferences, it is recommended that schools adopt policies mandating the inclusion of these strategies as part of regular instructional practices. Additionally, professional development programs should be implemented to train teachers on how to design and execute activities that enhance inferential reasoning. By embedding such practices in the curriculum, schools can systematically develop students' higher-order thinking skills and improve overall literacy outcomes.

To enhance reading comprehension in **practice**, it is recommended that teachers should incorporate storytelling and role-playing as regular classroom activities to strengthen students' inferential comprehension skills. Specific focus should be given to designing exercises that challenge students to deduce implied meanings, interpret figurative language, and connect contextual clues within texts. For instance, teachers can use guided discussions, role-play scenarios, and targeted questions to encourage students to draw inferences from characters' actions, motivations, or underlying themes. Additionally, formative assessments that emphasize inferential reasoning should be utilized to monitor progress and provide feedback, ensuring consistent improvement in this critical aspect of reading comprehension.

Considering the unique educational context of Indonesia, three potential titles for future studies are suggested. First, **"The Role of Cultural Context in Storytelling: Enhancing Reading Comprehension among Indonesian Elementary Students"** could explore how incorporating local cultural elements into storytelling can improve reading comprehension. Second, **"Adapting Role-Playing Techniques to Improve Critical Thinking and Reading**

Comprehension Skills in Indonesian Middle School Students" could investigate the effectiveness of role-playing in developing critical thinking alongside reading comprehension in this age group. Lastly, ***Evaluating the Effectiveness of Interactive Learning Strategies in Bridging the Urban-Rural Gap in Reading Comprehension among Indonesian Students***" could focus on how interactive approaches like storytelling and role-playing can help close the educational achievement gap between urban and rural students in Indonesia.

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